

Incorporating A Priori Oracle MPC Knowledge into Model Predictive Control Algorithms

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Abstract - In this paper, a priori situational knowledge about motion cueing for recorded test drives is incorporated into a model predictive motion cueing algorithm to move a driving simulator with greater foresight. By training a neural network on offline computed Oracle MPC motion cueing sequences, data-driven references are obtained that guide the real-time-capable MPC algorithm. The effectiveness of this modified MPC algorithm is evaluated in emergency braking scenarios near intersections by comparing the cueing error to a baseline.

Keywords: Driving Simulators, Motion Cueing, Model Predictive Control, MLP Prediction

Introduction

Dynamic driving simulators replicate not only visual and auditory stimuli but also vestibular stimuli, which are critical for creating realistic driving experiences and minimizing motion sickness. Motion cueing algorithms translate virtual vehicle movements into the simulator's limited physical motion range. The use of Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithms has become a central focus of motion cueing research in recent years. The concept is based on the prediction of vestibularly perceptible stimuli, typically accelerations and angular velocities. Modern MPC approaches typically begin by predicting the driver's behavior within a defined prediction horizon. Based on this prediction, vehicle responses and perceived variables can be calculated. An optimization process then determines the optimal sequence of simulator motions to match the predicted perceived quantities as closely as possible.

Statistical knowledge about the relation between motion cueing, track, and driving situations can be used to more efficiently exploit the motion capabilities of the simulator. For filter-based motion algorithms, it has been shown that heuristic or statistical a priori knowledge can be used to favorably position the simulator according to the driving situation or the upcoming road course. This concept is referred to as prepositioning in literature (Eppink, et al., 2023; Hansson, et al., 2015). Such knowledge can be derived heuristically from experience or statistically from recorded simulator drives. Oracle MPC algorithms, which optimize simulator motion based on recorded driving data, have been used to build route-based knowledge for this purpose (Ellensohn, et al., 2020).

Although MPC algorithms can dynamically account for the course of the track and driving situation, their performance is limited by uncertainties about the future and computational real-time limitations. Therefore, using a prediction model based on a priori knowledge about correlations between driving situations and simulator positions allows for a more direct interpretation, effectively bypassing the driver-

Figure 1: Inclusion of Oracle MPC data for MPC state reference prediction

vehicle feedback loop, as depicted in figure 1. This does not mean that the prediction of perceived quantities should be omitted, but rather that a priori motion cueing knowledge can be used to better assess the simulator's state through the prediction horizon.

Research Question

This scientific research is based on the hypothesis that the performance of MPC-based motion cueing can be enhanced by incorporating statistical motion cueing knowledge related to the driving situation. To address this hypothesis, this paper demonstrates how statistical motion cueing knowledge can be collected and favorable simulator states can be predicted from the current driving state. In addition, a method for effectively integrating this knowledge into the MPC formulation is presented.

Methodology

A series of human test drives was recorded on a 6-DoF hexapod driving simulator. In these drives, participants approached a crossing where they were surprised by occluded vehicles and performed emergency braking near the intersection. The study design enables prediction of the braking maneuver based on the vehicle's distance to the crossing and

its velocity. For each trial, an offline Oracle MPC motion cueing algorithm, based on the implementation by (KATLIAR, et al., 2018), computed near-optimal simulator motions using knowledge of the trajectory ahead. Inspired by the work of Alexander Lamprecht, et al. (2021), a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with 2 hidden layers was trained on 15 recorded drives of this dataset. The neural network (NN) predicts the inertial reference, specifically longitudinal acceleration and pitch rate, across a 0.5s sampled prediction horizon. A model input consisting of a 10s history of longitudinal accelerations and pitch rates, which are sampled at 0.5s intervals, as well as the current vehicle speed, vehicle position and vehicle pitch is generated from each time step of the 100Hz recordings.

In this work, the NN model predicts not only the inertial reference, but also the simulator state reference, which includes the simulator's x-position and pitch rate over the same prediction horizon. The simulator state reference was trained on simulator motion data generated by the Oracle MPC algorithm for the recorded test drives. Although the neural network task to predict the inertial reference for the MPC controller is independent of the prediction of oracle simulator states, a single network that predicts the inertial and state reference together was trained in this work for better comparability of results. The simulator reference values predicted by the NN model are incorporated into the MPC's cost function as the MPC's state error. The modified cost function penalizes deviations from the reference simulator trajectory, predicted by the neural network, promoting poses associated with favorable cueing in the past.

Results and Discussion

The benefit of incorporating the NN-predicted Oracle-MPC state reference into the MPC controller was evaluated through a series of tests. The baseline consists of MPC Motion Cueing Algorithms using three different strategies for inertial prediction.

- **Constant Prediction:** Assumes constant acceleration over the prediction horizon.
- **Oracle Prediction:** Uses the actual future trajectory (from recorded data) to provide perfect foresight of inertial inputs.
- **Neural Network Prediction:** Utilizes the trained model to estimate future inertial quantities based on past data.

In a second step, these inertial prediction MPC variants were extended by including simulator state predictions from the neural network. Figure 2 compares the baseline variants against MPC controllers extended by incorporating the state prediction. For comparison, the sum of the RMSE for accelerations and angular rates in each DoF compared to the inertial reference was computed. To align with the weighting in the MPC cost function, angular rate errors were scaled by a factor of 10.

Compared to the constant-acceleration baseline, the enhanced MPC controller reduced cueing RMSE by 11.51, indicating a notable improvement. In contrast, the NN-based inertial reference variant saw only a modest RMSE reduction of 0.34. Surprisingly, the MPC modifications for the Oracle reference led to an RMSE increase of 1.96, suggesting that the integration of NN-predicted state references can have an adverse effect on cueing performance.

Figure 2: Comparison of baselines against modified MPC algorithms taking predicted state references into account

Conclusions and Implications

The analysis using an MPC model with constant inertial prediction shows that the predicted simulator state trajectories can improve the motion cueing quality considerably. Despite the increased complexity introduced by this MPC extension, the anticipated improvements in performance were not fully realized. Especially for the most practically relevant configurations, NN and oracle inertial prediction, the RMSE was only marginally decreased and even increased in the oracle case. Since the results depend on the mpc parametrization and NN prediction quality, tuning could potentially lead to more significant improvements in motion cueing performance. Further investigation into simulator setups featuring DoFs with extended travel ranges, such as longitudinal or lateral rails, may reveal greater benefits through enhanced foresight resulting from this method. Note, that the presented results depend on the route and scenario.

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